

CONTENTS

Sr.No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Page No.	Download
01	Md. Abu Shahid Abdullah	Ethnic Othering in True Lies	1-10	PDF

02	Ajaz Ahmad Hajam	English Language Learning: Exploring Cultural and Lingual Identity of Indian English Language Learners	11-14	PDF
03	Altaf Ahmad Bhat	Tolerance and Resistance: Multiple Shapes of Indian Women in Desirable Daughters and Difficult Daughters	15-20	PDF
04	Amar Singh & Prof. Anita Singh	(Re)Reading The Exorcist	21-23	PDF
05	Arshed Irshad	A Modernistic Urge behind a Post-modern Impulse: Sam Shepard's Buried Child	24-27	PDF
06	Dr. Asit Panda	Towards an Indigenization of Theatre: Appropriation of African Myths, Rituals and Beliefs in the Plays of Wole Soyinka	28-35	PDF
07	Asma Arshi	Chetan Bhagat's Revolution 2020: A Love Triangle, Corruption, Moral Perversion and a Journey of Self Identification	36-38	PDF
08	Prof. Shakuntala Kunwar & Bharti Silswal	Why Adiga, Not Ghosh	39-45	PDF
09	Dr. Vandana Bhatt	Search for Identity in Bharati Mukherjee's Wife	46-49	PDF
10	Bishnu Prasad Gogoi	Rediscovering Tragic Female Characters in D. H. Lawrence's Sons and Lovers	50-54	PDF
11	Dr. Dhruv Shankar	Catholic and Napoleonic Awakening in Graham	55-62	PDF

		Greene's Brighton Rock		
12	Dr. Divya Pandey	Elizabeth Bennet as the Embodiment of the New Woman in Jane Austen's Pride and Prejudice	63-68	PDF
13	Divya. C	Attitude of Teachers towards Their Profession and Administration	69-74	PDF
14	Sagarika Dutta	Traumatic History, Traumatic Memory: Fiction and its Therapeutic Value in Shonali Bose's Amu	75-82	PDF
15	Anindita Ganguly	Subdued Echoes of Violence and Terror in Dina Mehta's Getting Away with Murder and Brides Are Not for Burning	83-88	PDF
16	Gitanjali Gogoi	Countering Conrad: A Reading of Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart	89-97	PDF
17	C.Govindaraj, Dr. V. Kundavi & R.Lissy	Joyce Carol Oates' Portrayal of America as a Garden of Earthly Delights without Any Heavenly Grace	98-103	PDF
18	Hindol Palit	The Seize Within: A Political Investigation of Eastern Europe with Three Productions of Hamlet	104-107	PDF
19	Iman Ghosh	Imagining Bombay and London: In Search of Post-Colonial Hybrid Identity in Midnight's Children and The Satanic Verses	108-111	PDF
20	Insha Siraj	Affirming Black Womanist Self in Alice Walker's The	112-114	PDF

		Color Purple		
21	Kalpana Nehere & Dr. P. R. Bhabad	Arun Joshi's The Foreigner: A Feministic Analysis	115-124	PDF
22	Karthika. J	Gender Politics in the Plays of Mahesh Dattani	125-129	PDF
23	Dr. J.P. Kaushik	Transmogrification of Gandhian Views and Values in Contemporary Indian English Fiction	130-140	PDF
24	Nargis Khan	Using Narrative Study for Affective Understanding of Text in Ruskin Bond's The Thief	141-146	PDF
25	Ram Lalit	Quest for Home and Memory: Rohinton Mistry's Novels: A Diasporic Study	147-150	PDF
26	Madhukar Wankhede	Gandhi on Untouchability and Anand's Untouchable	151-154	PDF
27	Dr. Madhuri Sood	Woman Empowerment in R. K. Narayan's Novels	155-157	PDF
28	Dr. Milan Swaroop Sharma & Dr. Ram Avtar Vats	The Hero and the Hero-Worship: The Immortals of Meluha	158-161	PDF
29	Minaxi Brahma	Missing North-East [Indian] Elements in Anjum Hasan's Poetry	162-167	PDF
30	Mousim Mondal	Colour of One's Own	168-171	PDF
31	Nafisa Zargar	Multiculturalism and Fractured White Identity in Hanif Kureishi's Gabriel's Gift	172-184	PDF
32	Nakul Berwal	Marriage and Social Change: A Study of Three Plays	185-191	PDF
33	Naz Zarger	The Subaltern Speaks: Short Stories by Indian	192-200	PDF

		Women Writers		
34	Neetika	Re-Representation of Mahabharata's Draupadi in Pratibha Ray's Yajnaseni: The Story of Draupadi	201-207	PDF
35	Dr. Rajneesh Pandey	Manju Kapur's Difficult Daughters: A Postmodern Feminist Urge for Autonomy	208-213	PDF
36	Dr. Bharati Patnaik	Diasporic Crisis of Dual Identity in Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake	214-216	PDF
37	Pooja Khali	Eco-Spiritualism in Rabindranath Tagore's Gitanjali	217-221	PDF
38	Pracheta Bakshi	Empire, Nation, Gender in Audre Lorde's Zami: A New Spelling of My Name and Maxine Hong-Kingston's The Woman Warrior: Memoirs of a Girlhood Among Ghosts	222-227	PDF
39	M. Premalatha & Dr. T. Deivasigamani	Image of Lesbianism in Shobha De's Starry Nights and Strange Obsession	228-234	PDF
40	Pritam V. Pathe	Mental Deformity Interpreted in Vijay Tendulkar's Sakharam Binder	235-238	PDF
41	Rajni Dwivedi	Archetypal Deconstruction in Mahasweta Devi's Draupadi	239-245	PDF
42	Rakesh Kumar	The Grave – Digger's Scene: Hamlet's Journey to the Dead Souls	246-250	PDF
43	Dr. Ram Avtar Vats & Rakhi	Woman – Contrivance of Life Force: Arms and the	251-253	PDF

	Sharma	Man		
44	Ramesh K. G.	Subverting the Metanarratives of Kemalism: Orhan Pamuk's The White Castle as a Postmodern Narrative Revolt	254-259	PDF
45	Amit Ray	Bombay and Mumbai, the City in Transition and its 'Secret History' through Jeet Thayil's Narcopolis	260-264	PDF
46	Ruchi Tomar	Deconstructing 'Self' and 'Other' with Reference to Joseph Conrad's Heart of Darkness	265-269	PDF
47	Dr. Sabreen Ahmed	Gender and the North East India: A Postcolonial Feminist Reading of Mitra Phukan's The Collector's Wife	270-275	PDF
48	Yugeshwar Sah	Communal Harmony and Peace-Building through Education	276-284	PDF
49	Sandeep Kaur	Ngugi's Politics of Language: Background and Context	285-290	PDF
50	R.Sangeetha & J.Sarah Shekkina	A Subaltern Study of The God of Small Things	291-295	PDF
51	Sapna Bhargav	Putting the Puzzle Together: An Analysis of Paul Auster's City of Glass as an Anti-Detective Novel	296-300	PDF
52	Sarap N.S., Mahadik R.P. & Mehta P.G.	Evaluation of UG English Language Course Materials Offered by SAUs in Maharashtra State	301-305	PDF
53	Shagufta	Negotiating Patriarchy,	306-316	PDF

	Parween	Women's Empowerment and Fundamentalism in Manju Kapur's A Married Woman		
54	Dr. Shweta Saxena	A Room of his Own: Quest for Identity vis-à-vis Female Hegemony in Naipaul's A House for Mr. Biswas	317-319	PDF
55	Soumita Adhikary	The Translation of the Subaltern Discourse to the Dominant Episteme in Mahasweta Devi's The Book of the Hunter	320-324	PDF
56	Souvik Biswas	'Among All the Ghosts and Memories': Anguish and Alienation in Ingmar Bergman's The Silence	325-331	PDF
57	Suchismita Sarkar	Influence of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita's Concept of 'Sthitapragna' and 'Nishkamkarmayoga' on Kipling's True Man in If	332-335	PDF
58	Sujit Malick	Augusto Boal's Theatre of the Oppressed: A Theatre of Marginalized People in India	336-340	PDF
59	Swati Mane	Nature and Ecocriticism in Hullabaloo in the Guava Orchard	341-345	PDF
60	Taniya Neogi	Paule Marshall's Brown Girl, Brownstones: A Novel of Growth beyond Brownness and Brownstones	346-352	PDF
61	Ujaan Ghosh	Science, Scientism and Nazism	353-359	PDF
62	Dr. Uttam B	Optimism in Africa with	360-365	PDF

	Sonkamble	Reference to Smith's Motswana Fiction: A Reinterpretation		
63	Varshika Srivastava	Feminism in Anita Desai's Fasting Feasting	366-369	PDF
64	Vasanthi Vasireddy	The Struggle for Identity in Anita Desai's Bye-Bye Blackbird	370-372	PDF
65	Vinod Kumar Vaishya	Cross-Culture and Theme of Alienation in Arun Joshi's The Strange Case of Billy Biswas	373-378	PDF
66	Dr. Gunjun Agarwal & Monika Yadav	Girish Karnad: A Critic of Religious Fundamentalism	379-383	PDF
Poetry				
01	Akanksha Chaudhary	The Little Vibrant World	384-385	PDF
02	Babita Chakraborty	Hard Reality	386	PDF
03	Ruchi Chopra	Am Still Boss!	387-388	PDF
04	Deeya Bhattacharya	A Sparrow's Ordeal	389-390	PDF
05	Farah Siddiqui	Near to God	391-393	PDF
06	Ishfaq Manzoor Malik	Dream- A Lyrical	394	PDF
07	Juan Pablo Duboué	The Father you Served	395-397	PDF
08	Karthika. J	The Vision	398	PDF
09	Leena Sharma	Dreams	399	PDF
10	Michael Lee Johnson	Southside, Chicago Town Whore	400-401	PDF
11	Dr. Nagabhushan Moolky	I am so minute....	402	PDF
12	Mrinal Kanti Ghosh	In Search of anotherWorld	403-404	PDF

13	Naresh Annem	Into the Sky of Hopes	405-406	PDF
14	Raghavendra Nayak	Everything for you, Hamlet	407	PDF
15	Parminder Singh	Butterfly	408	PDF
16	Pretty John .P	Faces	409	PDF
17	Ranjani Neriya	Violated	410	PDF
18	Shijomon Kunnel Varghese	Editing	411	PDF
19	Sunaina Jain	Silence	412-413	PDF
20	Zev Torres	After Ripping off the Wrapping Paper	414	PDF
Fiction				
01	Frank Zahn	Mother Finally Made It	415-417	PDF
02	Jamie Spears	Old Henry	418	PDF
03	Jason Constantine Ford	A New Day In A New Year	419-428	PDF
04	Kenneth Robbins	A Normal Christmas	429-433	PDF
05	Ramesh Chandra Tiwari	You dilly-dally?	434-442	PDF
06	Dr. Riyad Manqoush	The Fence	443-447	PDF
Book Review				
01	Mudasir Altaf Bhat	The Half Mother by Shahnaz Bashir	448-450	PDF
02	Deepika Rani	The One Night Affair and Other Stories by Madhulika Chauhan	451-452	PDF
03	Gagan B. Purohit	Sukama and Other Poems by Nandini Sahu	453-456	PDF
04	Joie Bose	These Hills Called Home: Stories from a War Zone by Temsula Ao	457-460	PDF
05	Dr. Vinita Singh Chawdhry	The Plays of Girish Karnad: A Study in Myths and Gender by Abhishek Kosta	461-462	PDF

06	Sagarika Dash	The Dark Abode by Dr. Sarojini Sahoo	463-466	PDF
07	Varsha Singh	NINE: Vengeance of the Warrior (Book Two) by Shobha Nihalani	467-468	PDF
Interview				
01	Dr. Ajit Kumar	An Interview with Dr. Ampat Varghese Koshy, a Poet from India	469-474	PDF